

METHODS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS LESSONS

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Abstract.

The quality of physical education is interconnected with educational principles, and the effectiveness (result, consequence) arising from it has a positive effect on the improvement of the quality of training in the process of physical culture education, which is the main content of our article. The article is intended for future physical education teachers who are specialists in the field.

Key words.

lesson, physical education lesson, education, physical education classes, lesson schedule, physical education, educational process, educational groups, physical exercises.

INTRODUCTION

Physical education as a component of general education has its own characteristics in terms of social education and living conditions. For this reason, in the field of physical education and sports, the history of physical education and sports management are taught as subjects in higher and secondary special educational institutions. The importance of this science in the implementation of the national personnel training program, state education standards, the state program of a healthy generation and the processes related to them is very great. The history of physical education and the science of sports management serve to train specialist personnel and enrich the theoretical knowledge of the population, especially pupils and students. In this, the theory and methodology of physical education, pedagogy, history and other sciences, especially sports sciences (specialization), are closely related and rely on their content, purpose and tasks. On this basis, it performs the following tasks, namely:[1]

- introduction to the physical education of ancient ancestors and peoples of the recent past;

- providing information on the history of the formation of modern sports, development processes and the organization of national sports events;

- to describe the sports that are popular among the peoples of the world and the activities of the developed countries that pay attention to it;
- Provide details about the historical periods of development of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan;
- to reveal the contents, goals and tasks of the international sports and Olympic movement;
- teaching the ways (methods) of learning this subject;
- commenting on the great future sports development, etc.

It has been scientifically, theoretically and pedagogically proven that physical training and sports have been used as the most important socio-educational and training in the world of human history[2]. Physical education, which is considered an important component of physical education, and its factors (games, various exercises, competitions, travel, health-giving means of nature: water, air, sun, cleanliness-hygiene, etc.) in the social and living conditions of our oldest ancestors purposefully used. "Avesta", "Tomaris", "Alpomish", "Gorogli", "Forty girls" and many other religious, cultural, artistic works and historical sources testify about them. Such resources can be found in almost all countries of the world. Recognizing the healing properties of physical education, a number of great scientists from Europe and Asia worked with selflessness and left their creative and scientific heritage. Among them, one of the great scientists of the East, Abu Ali ibn Sina, has some (physical) training, scientifically and practically proven in the "Laws of Medicine", the most important reality. P.F.Lesgaft (Russia), who appreciated his ideas at a high level and with his theory of physical education, took a worthy place in the history of physical education in the world. It should be noted that since the second half of the 19th century, the training of specialist personnel with knowledge of anatomy and physiology has been started in the field of physical education. This system was perfectly developed during the time of the former union, and new guidelines for personnel training, taking into account the essence of sports, were implemented.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The topics included in the structural structure of the training manual, according to their content and orientation, are "General principles of physical education and sports pedagogy", "Educational theory in the field of physical education and sports", "Physical education and It consists of sections such as "Theory of education in the field of sports", "Management of physical training and sports education systems", "Basics of pedagogical activity of the pedagogue in the field of sports". Particular attention is paid to ensuring mutual consistency and

logicality between ideas when revealing the themes expressed in the chapters. In the description of the topics, the views of the Eastern thinkers, the use of the foundations of folk pedagogy, serve to educate a well-rounded person and a qualified specialist. In the creation of the textbook, the authors took into account the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" as well as the "Law on Physical Education and Sports". they relied on opinions. In addition, the general foundations of the science of "Physical education and sports pedagogy" were explained from the point of view of the existing social necessity; The system of professional education in the field of physical education and sports, a methodological manual for undergraduates, Skutin A.V., 2014, Physical education in general educational institutions in the context of the introduction of the second generation federal state educational standard and 3 hours of physical education teaching, Nazarkina N.I., Nikolaicheva I.M., 2014, Physical education, Textbook for 3rd graders of general secondary schools, Makhkamdjanov K., Khojaev F., 2016, Physical education, General secondary textbook for 2nd grade students, Makhkamdjanov K., Khodjayev F., 2018.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Active teaching methods - methods that stimulate students' cognitive activity; they are mainly based on communication, which includes free exchange of ideas on ways to solve a particular problem, and are characterized by high student engagement. The methodological basis of the introduction of active teaching methods into the educational process of universities is the theoretical ideas and approaches, such as the personal-activity approach, in which the individual is considered as a subject of activity (Ananiev B.G., Vygotsky L.S., Leontiev A.N., Rubinshtein S.L., etc.); "constructivist" (Vygotsky L.S., Palinksar A., Piaget J., etc.); socio-cultural theory (Vygotsky L.S.); theory of programmed education (Kupisevich Ch., Landa A.N., Skinner B.F., Talyzina N.F., etc.); developmental education (Davydov V.V., Zankov L.V., Elkonin D.B. and others); contextual education (Verbitsky A.A.); individual activity and person-oriented education (Zimnyaya I.A., Yakimanskaya I.S., etc.); theory of cognitive flexibility (Anderson R., Coleson R., Spiro R., Feltovich P., etc.); metacognitive learning (Brause J. and Wood D., Brunner D., Boostrom R., Wertch D., Cole M., Russell B., Halpern D., etc.), as well as approaches to educational and pedagogical innovation: competency-based approach; problem education (Arkhangelsky S.I., Dewey D., Lerner L.Ya., Matyushkin A.M., Makhmutov M.I., Skatkin M.N. and others); technology of full absorption of knowledge (Blum B., Carroll J., etc.); multi-level educational

technology (Kalmykova Z.I., Cohen E., Carroll J., Platonov K.K. and others); collective learning technology (V.K. Dyachenko, V.B. Lebedintsev, A.G. Rivin, etc.); technology of modular education (Muravieva A.A., Kuznetsova Yu.N., Chervyakova T.N., Yutsyavichene P. and others) and technology of using active teaching methods (Abramova I.G., Arutyunov Yu.S., Birshtein M. M., Gerasimov B.N., Grudzinskaya E.Yu., Mariko V.V., Zhukov R.F., Komarov V.F., Lifshits A.L., Panfilova A.P., Platov V.Ya., Porkhovnik Yu.M., Rybalsky V.I., Smolkin A.M., Syroejin A.M., T.V.koy, Syroejin A.M., T.V.). During the implementation of active teaching methods, qualities and qualities of a person such as social adaptation are successfully formed; communicative ability; willingness to take responsibility for group activities; the ability to promote and formulate ideas, projects; readiness to make correct and non-standard decisions; the ability to avoid mistakes and their repetition; to express one's thoughts clearly, competently and confidently; the ability to predict the consequences of actions; ability to effectively organize personal time and activities.

Extracurricular forms of physical exercise are fundamentally different from academic classes in that they are periodic, unsystematic, one-time or individual, compared to classes.[3] Many variants of such schemes have been improved, and to date, from the summation of the four main components of the lesson - physical exercises included in the text of the lesson outline, changes that occur in the student's organism by performing them in the lesson (physiological, biological, biomechanical, psychological and etc.), during the lesson, the activity of the teacher and the students expressed the content of the physical education lesson. They are: The mentioned aspects are interconnected with each other and they are called the characteristic components (aspects) of the physical education lesson. Another component of the content of the physical education lesson is physical exercises planned for use as educational material in the preparatory, main, and final parts of the lesson. Functional, mental, pedagogical and other changes occur in the students' organism by performing these exercises in class. This is the second component of the content of the physical education lesson. The next (third and fourth) components representing the content of the lesson are the activities of the teacher conducting the lesson and the students participating in the lesson. organization of their activity in the lesson, teaching methods selected for the educational process are embodied. The effectiveness of the lesson depends on the mentioned components and the principles of their implementation. Physical exercises included in the lesson are the largest characteristic component of the lesson content. But such a concept is one-sided, it serves as the subject of activities during the lesson for

students in the tasks of education, health, education and application of the principle[4].

RESULTS

The average indicators of pedagogical skill of these physical education teachers varied from 5.98 to 6.35 points. The average estimated indicators of physical fitness of students of different classes were in the range of 3.87-5.43 points, motor aspiration - 3.67-5.45 points, learning ability - 4.78-5.23 points, motor talent - 4.87- 5.28 points. Teaching the technique of motor actions was most effectively carried out in 5th grade students in rope climbing in three steps - 6.8 conventional units. units, 6th grade - rope climbing in two stages - 6.2 conventional units. units, 7th grade - somersault back into half split (girls) - 6.2 conventional units. unit, long jump from 9-11 takeoff steps (boys) - 5.8 arb. units, 8th grade - combinations of acrobatic exercises - 6.7 conventional units. units (boys) and 6.5 conventional units. units (girls), 9th grade - attacking blow with oncoming passes - 5.6 conventional units. units, 10th grade - receiving the ball after serving - 5.6 arb. units, 11th grade - serving the ball through the net from behind the front line - 5.8 conventional units. units Parameters of the levels of evaluative indicators of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions: low - 2.7 arb. units, below average - 4.0 arb. units, average - 5.4 arb. units, above average - 6.8 arb. units, high - 8.5 arb. units For students of 5-11th grades, most of the indicators of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions are at a level below the average, however, as they study at school, an insignificant increase in these characteristics is manifested, which is due to the continuity of the studied exercises of the school program. The effectiveness of learning the technique of motor actions was higher when performing gymnastic exercises (standard conditions) and significantly lower in game exercises (probabilistic conditions). In our opinion, it is necessary to develop methods of teaching the technique of motor actions for various conditions, which will significantly increase the effectiveness of the educational process in physical culture in secondary educational institutions. The proposed method for assessing the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions makes it possible to distribute exercises according to the degree of mastering complexity, to identify the required number of physical education lessons for studying a motor task. The results of our study show that the analyzed characteristics of the success in solving motor tasks are variable: the coefficients of variation vary from 27.0% (expert assessment of the physical culture and sports work of a physical education teacher) to 58.2% (physical fitness of students). As they study at school, the indicators of assessing the physical fitness of students (from 5.34 to 3.92 points) and motor

aspiration (from 5.35 to 3.70 points) deteriorate. The greatest value of learning motor actions was obtained from pupils of the 5th-7th grades (5.06 ± 0.29 points). The advantage of boys in terms of motor aspiration is manifested, and the assessments of the ability to learn motor actions of boys and girls did not differ significantly. Determining the indicators of success in solving a motor task for each teacher and student, it is possible to plan an individual trajectory of the learning process in a secondary educational institution. According to our data, in the structure of motor endowment of students, the following priorities of the significance of the components are determined: grades 5-7 - learning ability of students (20.7%), grades 8-9 - motor aspiration (21.3%), grades 10-11 - physical readiness (20.3%) - boys, learning ability (21.4%) - girls. In 5th-7th grade boys, the indicators of learning to move are interconnected with the characteristics of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions ($r=0.512$) and physical fitness ($r=0.433$), motor aspiration - with the indicators of physical culture and sports activities of the teacher ($r=0.437$).

In girls of these classes, such interdependence is manifested between the characteristics of learning ability and indicators of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions ($r=0.524$), physical culture and sports activities of the teacher and motor aspiration ($r=0.411$), physical fitness and expert assessment ($r=0.405$). For boys of 8th-9th grades, the indicators of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions are interconnected with the indicators of students' learning ability ($r=0.537$), physical fitness - with the characteristics of expert assessment ($r=0.474$) and learning ability of motor actions ($r=0.472$). In girls, the mutual influence was found between the results of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions and learning ability of students ($r=0.496$), motor aspiration ($r=0.464$) and motor giftedness ($r=0.432$), learning characteristics and the results of motor giftedness ($r=0.430$). In boys of 10-11th grades, significant relationships are manifested between the indicators of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions and the characteristics of motor aspiration ($r = 0.527$), physical fitness and expert assessments ($r = 0.503$), and in girls - between the characteristics of the effectiveness of teaching the technique of motor actions and learnability of students ($r=0.512$), motor aspiration and motor talent ($r=0.430$)

CONCLUSION

One of the leading, main principle factors of lesson effectiveness is the activity of the teacher, the next component of the lesson content, which includes all his professional activities during the lesson: assigning homework and explaining it, being able to state the exact task of the lesson and organize its solution, constantly

to control, analyze their activities, as well as direct the activities of the students to the right path, keep the relationship between them in the center of attention, and direct, manage, control the activities of the students to effectively solve the lesson tasks includes theoretical, practical aspects and basic situations of the educational process, such as assessment of mastery.

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